

Integrating AI and RDF Knowledge Graphs with MITRE ATT&CK for CTI Insights

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Abstract. The general need exists for robust threat detection methods that adapt to new and evolving cyber threats. In this paper, we propose a method that uses RDF-based knowledge graphs and AI to improve detection and classification of attacks. Our approach transforms security logs into RDF and maps them to the MITRE ATT&CK framework. We also address sensitive data concerns, such as IP addresses, by applying privacy measures. Our results show that AI-driven analysis and knowledge graphs can enhance cyber threat intelligence (CTI), while respecting privacy regulations.

Keywords: RDF · Knowledge Graphs · Cybersecurity · CTI · MITRE ATT&CK.

1 Introduction

Cybersecurity is rapidly evolving, with threats becoming more advanced. Organizations rely on Cyber Threat Intelligence (CTI), but legacy security frameworks struggle against evolving attacker tactics [12, 13]. Traditional rule-based detection fails to identify sophisticated attack patterns, as security event logs are often fragmented. Smarter, more adaptive measures are needed [12].

Classic cybersecurity methods lag behind emerging threats. Static systems struggle to detect new techniques, and dispersed security logs hinder correlation. Our solution leverages RDF-based knowledge graphs and AI-driven analytics to structure and link CTI, enhancing cyber threat detection with a scalable, adaptive approach [2].

This paper proposes integrating RDF-based knowledge graphs with AI to improve CTI. Our approach improves the structuring, correlation, and interpretation of cybersecurity event logs while leveraging the MITRE ATT&CK framework for automated threat mapping. By integrating AI techniques, we enhance the adaptability and accuracy of cybersecurity threat detection, addressing key limitations of existing approaches. The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 reviews related work. Section 3 details our methodology, including the integration of RDF-based knowledge graphs and AI-driven techniques for automated threat intelligence. It also presents evaluation results and

discusses the limitations of our approach. Additionally, in Section 4 we provide a preliminary evaluation of the proposed framework. Finally, Section 5 provides conclusions and outlines future research directions.

2 Related work

Cybersecurity frameworks have been pivotal in enhancing defenses and understanding cyber threats. Prototypes like the Diamond Model and Lockheed Martin Cyber Kill Chain established structured methods for analyzing cyber incidents. The Cyber Kill Chain outlines attack stages from reconnaissance to exfiltration, helping organizations detect and mitigate threats at each step [6], while the Diamond Model links adversaries, capabilities, infrastructure, and victims for a deeper understanding of attack dynamics [9]. Though both models have advanced threat analysis, they often lack the granularity needed for real-time threat detection and response.

MITRE ATT&CK is a globally accessible knowledge base of adversary tactics and techniques based on real-world observations. Developed by MITRE Corporation, it provides a structured approach to understanding cyber threats and adversarial behaviors, helping organizations across government, industry, and academia develop threat models, strengthen cybersecurity strategies, and enhance defense operations [8]. By categorizing tactics, techniques, and procedures (TTPs), ATT&CK enables security teams to analyze and respond to threats more effectively [3].

A key strength of ATT&CK is its taxonomy, which systematically organizes adversary actions within a structured matrix. Unlike traditional models that may lack the granularity to capture evolving cyber threats, ATT&CK allows dynamic mapping of adversary behaviour to predefined attack techniques, making it invaluable for CTI and defense planning [1,5,10]. Its versatility across IT, cloud security and industrial control systems (ICS) further enhances its applicability [5]. Additionally, ATT&CK provides a common language for cybersecurity practitioners, facilitating collaboration, knowledge sharing and standardization [7], while its adoption in cybersecurity education and training helps professionals develop hands-on skills in threat detection and response [4].

Compared to other frameworks, ATT&CK offers a more flexible and adaptive approach than the Cyber Kill Chain, which follows a linear model and may oversimplify complex attack sequences [9]. While the Diamond Model focuses on relationships between attack elements, ATT&CK emphasizes specific adversarial actions, offering a detailed perspective on threat behavior [6]. However, ATT&CK relies on continuous updates and community contributions, sometimes leading to inconsistencies in tracking emerging threats [9]. Moreover, while it excels in threat modeling and detection, it lacks built-in mitigation strategies, requiring integration with other cybersecurity frameworks for a more comprehensive defense posture.

3 Methodology

This section describes the methodology used for transforming logs into RDF-based knowledge graphs, and integrating AI-driven techniques to enhance CTI. Figure 1 depicts the main steps of our methodology.

3.1 Data Processing Pipelines

Security logs originate from a variety of sources, including structured formats such as CSV and JSON, as well as unstructured formats like TXT and free-text reports. To ensure their usability, these logs must go through a structured preprocessing phase that includes normalization and transformation before they can be effectively integrated into cybersecurity analysis systems. To maintain consistency and data integrity, various normalization techniques should be also applied. Research has shown that relational databases can be successfully migrated to graph-based structures through transformation rules that preserve entity relationships and metadata integrity [10]. To enhance accuracy, the preprocessing phase should eliminate duplicate, incomplete, or damaged data along with extracting relevant security fields such as IP addresses, timestamps, and attack vectors.

Rather than creating distinct preprocessing workflows for every dataset, developing a generalised strategy capable of adapting across various contexts would be advantageous. A key part of this approach has to do with the use of AI tools that automate log processing. Large Language Models (LLMs) and NLP techniques contribute much to performing analysis on logs that are both semi-structured and unstructured, enabling not only classification but also extracting significant CTI [11]. These systems can process raw security data via API calls, extract key attributes, and transform logs into graph-compatible structures with the integration of AI-based services. This workflow ensures consistency and structuring of cybersecurity data before its integration into frameworks such as MITRE ATT&CK using AI-driven preprocessing. This enhanced approach fortifies an organisation's cybersecurity posture by enhancing the efficiency of automated CTI processing, attack detection, and cybersecurity event correlation.

3.2 Graph-Based Cybersecurity Models

Structured yet flexible data representation is essential for in-depth analysis of cybersecurity events and pattern identification. Our approach leverages RDF-based graph models to represent events, attack techniques, and network activities as structured relationships. These models offer significant advantages in semantic representation, interoperability, and advanced search capabilities, making them ideal for modeling complex cybersecurity datasets. Converting security logs into RDF-based knowledge graphs transforms threat intelligence into more structured and insightful forms. Unlike traditional databases where security incidents are recorded as isolated entries, RDF models reveal deeper connections between attack methods, Indicators of Compromise (IoCs), and system behaviors.

Fig. 1. Ontology alignment using LLMs for CTI. Illustrating the integration of source ontologies, domain ontologies, and vector databases using an LLM-driven pipeline for structured knowledge representation.

The process begins by standardizing security logs into a uniform structure. The data are converted into RDF triples—subject-predicate-object relationship tuples, facilitating analysis and cross-referencing between security events. A key innovation is the use of AI to map security incidents to known attack techniques in the MITRE ATT&CK framework. Large language models scan logs in real-time, identifying adversary Tactics, Techniques, and Procedures (TTPs) [3]. This enables dynamic monitoring, faster threat detection, and proactive responses from security teams. By representing security logs as RDF knowledge graphs, organizations gain a more comprehensive and integrated view of potential threats, enhancing both analysis capabilities and the ability to anticipate and prevent future attacks.

3.3 Structuring Security Event Logs in RDF Triple Stores

The organization and processing of security events are critical steps in identifying and understanding cyber threats. Security logs originate from diverse sources in various formats. We transform these into RDF-based knowledge graphs to achieve a unified, structured representation that is semantically rich, enables SPARQL queries, and facilitates mapping to the MITRE ATT&CK framework.

Security logs often contain PII such as IP addresses, MAC addresses, and email identifiers, raising privacy concerns. During the RDF transformation process, we identify and classify these fields, implementing anonymization methods like partial masking and controlled access policies to maintain compliance with regulations like GDPR while preserving essential threat intelligence. The preprocessing of security logs normalizes diverse data structures before conversion to RDF. For example, JSON logs from Network Security Groups contain security rules and IP addresses, TXT firewall logs record network flows with MAC addresses, and CSV email security logs include phishing attack information. Critical fields like timestamps, IP addresses, and attack types are extracted and mapped to appropriate ontologies, facilitating interconnection in the knowledge graph. Following are some data examples:

- **JSON logs from Network Security Groups contain security rules and IP addresses:**

JSON Logs from Network Security Groups

```
{
  "time": "2022-10-29T13:00:52Z",
  "systemId": "XXXX-XXXX-XXXX",
  "category": "NetworkSecurityGroupEvent",
  "primaryIPv4Address": "10.0.0.X",
  "macAddress": "XX-XX-XX-XX-XX-XX",
  "ruleName": "DefaultRule_AllowVnetOutBound",
  "direction": "Out",
  "priority": 65000,
  "type": "allow"
}
```

- **TXT firewall logs record network flows with MAC addresses:**

TXT Firewall Logs

```
Mar/07/2023 10:38:43 firewall,info prerouting: in:pppoe-XXX
out:(unknown 0), connection-state:established,
src-mac XX:XX:XX:XX:XX:XX, proto TCP,
XXX.XXX.XXX.XXX:443->XXX.XXX.XXX.XXX:58612, len 1492
```

- **CSV email security logs include phishing and spam attack information:**

Fig. 2. RDF representation of a cybersecurity event, linking security logs to MITRE ATT&CK techniques. This figure shows the way cybersecurity data is enriched and represented in RDF format, linking various pieces of information to a specific attack technique.

CSV Email Security Logs	
ReceivedTime,	SenderAddress, RecipientAddress, Subject, Type
"24/2/2023 12:56:36",	"newsletter@xxx.gr", "xxx@xxx.xx",
"Promotional Offer",	"Phish"

3.4 Converting Data to RDF Knowledge Graph

The data must be converted to RDF triples in order to be structured as knowledge graphs. This LLM-driven conversion follows a hierarchical model that includes the following steps:

- **Data Extraction** - Extracting critical fields.
- **Entity Mapping** - Mapping data to predefined ontologies (e.g. MITRE ATT&CK).
- **Triple Generation** - Generating RDF triples.

Logs from different sources follow distinct processing paths, depending on their nature. For example, a firewall log contains fields such as source IP, destination IP, protocol, and rule name, while an email security log records sender, recipient, and policy applied. Each type of log is parsed separately and transformed into RDF according to its corresponding ontology.

By converting the data into RDF knowledge graphs, we can exploit SPARQL queries for correlative threat analysis and automatic malware detection. The

ability to execute complex queries allows security analysts to identify relationships between attacks, IP addresses, firewall rules, and malicious domains. In Figure 2, we can see an example of semantic enrichment and structured representation of cybersecurity data, illustrating how different security events are linked to MITRE ATT&CK techniques.

The following SPARQL query detects all firewall events associated with known MITRE ATT&CK techniques. This query returns all firewall events, including the time point of each event, the source and destination IP addresses, and the relevant MITRE ATT&CK technique associated with each attack.

```

SPARQL Query

PREFIX cti: <http://example.org/cti#>
PREFIX mitre-attack: <https://attack.mitre.org/techniques/>

SELECT ?event ?time ?srcIp ?dstIp ?relatedAttack
WHERE {
  ?event rdf:type cti:NetworkSecurityGroupEvent ;
         cti:time ?time ;
         cti:srcIp ?srcIp ;
         cti:dstIp ?dstIp ;
         skos:related ?relatedAttack .
}

```

Figure ?? illustrates a cybersecurity knowledge graph, mapping security events (red nodes) to MITRE ATT&CK techniques (blue nodes). The central **NetworkSecurityGroupEvent** node connects multiple incidents, highlighting their relationships with known adversary tactics. Events are semantically linked through "related" and "type" edges, enabling automated correlation of firewall logs, attack techniques, and malicious behaviors. This representation enhances CTI by providing structured insights, improving detection, and supporting security analysts in identifying attack patterns. The graph demonstrates how RDF-based knowledge models can effectively structure and analyze cybersecurity data for more efficient and proactive incident response.

3.5 Handling and Identification of PII in RDF Knowledge Graphs

A critical requirement in our approach is the identification and proper handling of Personally Identifiable Information (PII) in security logs. Many security logs contain sensitive data—such as IP addresses, usernames, email addresses, and system identifiers—necessitating systematic detection and protection methods to comply with privacy regulations while maintaining analytical capabilities.

By transforming logs into RDF format and linking them to standardized CTI ontologies, we enhance automatic identification and classification of PII elements.


```

{
  "current_metadata_id": "XXX",
  "domain": "threat-intelligence",
  "pii_attributes": [
    {
      "dataset_element": "SenderAddress", // Detected Email Address, classified as Contact Information (DPV)
      "dpv_matches": [
        {
          "match": "https://w3id.org/dpv/dpv-owl/dpv-pd#EmailAddress", //Standardized mapping to DPV ontology
          "label": "Email Address",
          "description": "Information about Email address"
        }
      ]
    }
  ]
}

```

Fig. 4. Detected **SenderAddress** classified as PII and mapped to the DPV ontology for structured classification and privacy compliance.

After extracting RDF triples, a separate PII identification step automatically detects and categorizes sensitive information using the structured knowledge graph and its integration with MITRE ATT&CK. This approach ensures privacy compliance while maintaining the integrity of cybersecurity analysis.

In Figure 4, we illustrate an example where the detected **SenderAddress** is classified as PII and mapped to the DPV ontology for structured classification and privacy compliance.

This structured PII identification process ensures that sensitive data is properly classified and anonymized, mitigating privacy risks while maintaining the integrity of cybersecurity analysis.

4 Preliminary Evaluation

To assess the feasibility and impact of our proposed solution, we conducted an expert evaluation focusing on three key areas: system usefulness, threat mapping accuracy, and overall usability. Five cybersecurity experts with experience in CTI and knowledge graph applications evaluated our method using a formal framework. The results evaluated were derived through the application of our framework to representative scenarios, constructed from simulated organizational (university and software company) server logs. They scored the system on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = worst, 5 = best) across the targeted assessment areas. The experts found the system highly effective in improving threat detection and intelligence correlation, with an average rating of 4.2/5. The AI-driven classification produced promising results, though refinements were suggested for handling edge cases. The structured knowledge graph significantly enhanced security log interpretability, facilitating meaningful insights for analysts.

While performance was strong, experts recommended potential improvements, including expanded ontology coverage and refined entity recognition models to further enhance accuracy and applicability. The expert analysis con-

firms that combining AI and knowledge graphs improves cybersecurity processes. Though further enhancements would refine accuracy, our approach offers a well-organized and scalable framework for CTI.

5 Discussion and Conclusions

This short paper presented a methodology for processing cybersecurity event logs and structuring them into RDF-based Knowledge Graphs. By integrating AI-driven methods and the MITRE ATT&CK framework, our approach enhances automated detection and classification of cyber threats, simplifying the analysis, correlation, and response to security events.

Our results demonstrate that RDF knowledge graphs provide a more structured and semantically rich representation of cybersecurity events, improving both threat detection and correlation. AI models enable accurate mapping of raw security logs to known attack methods, facilitating timely threat intelligence analysis. The structured representation enhances querying capabilities, enabling faster threat investigations and improving security teams' response capabilities. Additionally, our approach to PII identification ensures compliance with data protection regulations without compromising cybersecurity data integrity.

Despite its advantages, our approach has limitations. Predefined ontologies require frequent updates to remain relevant as cyber threats evolve. AI models depend on high-quality annotated datasets, which are challenging to obtain and maintain. The computational cost of RDF transformation raises scalability concerns for large-scale applications. Finally, MITRE ATT&CK requires continuous updates to maintain effectiveness against evolving attack strategies.

Future research should focus on: (1) enhancing AI-based threat detection with real-time anomaly detection mechanisms; (2) extending knowledge graphs to include more dynamic attack patterns beyond pre-defined frameworks; (3) investigating federated learning for privacy-preserving PII detection; and (4) optimizing the RDF transformation pipeline for scalability with large cybersecurity datasets.

In conclusion, our methodology contributes to cybersecurity by providing a structured approach to CTI analysis. Integration of AI techniques and knowledge graphs enhances cybersecurity operations, improves threat detection, and strengthens proactive defense strategies. Addressing current limitations through future improvements will further solidify this approach as a valuable tool against cyber threats.

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